

“INSIDE THE SOVIET UNION: POWER, IDEOLOGY, AND COLLAPSE”

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20273921>

***Abstract.** USSR- Soviet Union Republics (1922-1991)- was the biggest country in the world. It was created during the revolution in October 1917 by the ideas and regime Vladimir Lenin and because of Civil war. USSR united several states of Central Asia such as; Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, and Kyrgyzstan. These states which were united was ruled and based on socialistic regime. During the period of USSR, it played the huge role in world politics especially after WW2. The leaders of republics were focused on communistic regimes. Economy was based on characterized by state control and investments, prices depend on natural resources. However, it faced some problems in the beginning because BOISHEVIKS had many enemies and decentralization of power. Despite on industrial, economic, educational and scientific improvements it is also faced very serious problems, in 1980 country faced political and economic crisis. Leaders of the USSR focused on militarization of the country and that’s why USSR participated in Cold War against United States of America. In addition, because of a wrong policy of Gorbachev such as nationalistic policy and “perestroika” which didn’t give any positive results. In 1991 Soviet Union collapsed and ceased to exist and left the heavy legacy to the post republics of the USSR and still it is playing the role in international politics and internal policy.*

***Key words:** USSR, revolution, regime, Cold War, problems.*

In 1922 in the territory of ex Russian empire were 6 republics: Ukraine, Belorussia, Aserbaijan, Armenia, and Georgia. But first, Vladimir Lenin thought that uniting the state under one leadership is the huge result of revolution. Moreover, Lenin was analyzing the ideas of Karl Marx and Fridrih Engels because they also supported the revolution and the ideas of socialism and communism. Vladimir Lenin hated bourgeoisie and wanted to destroy this type of system. He supported the plotetariat which means that working class is controlling the state. Lenin, was doing some research the ideas of Karl Marx and tried to connect with his own ideas with some little changes. In 30 december 1922 on the first congress of the council Representatives of RSFSR. In this declaration were discussed the main laws and agreements of uniting and creating the USSR. The agreement was focused on the relations between republics and center (Moscow). Vladimir Lenin wanted to create very big state and resist against imperialistic countries. What’s more, after USSR had been created the leaders wanted to create constitution. In 1924, on the second congress of the Representative Republics were officially announced the first constitution of USSR and the main idea was “ single union citizenship” which means that citizen of each republic is the citizen of the USSR. The official flag of the USSR, was approved by Presidium in 18th of April 1924.

<https://www.vecteezy.com/free-vector/ussr-flag>

Where we can see it's red color and hammer and sickle with a star. In USSR, was single party that controlled everything and they were socialists named in the begging (BOLSHEVIKS). There is a question why they choose this kind of name? “We really have a party, it is developing perfectly, it will come down and such as ugly word as the Bolsheviks, expressing absolutely nothing except for the purely accidental fact that at the Brussel-London congress of 1903 we had a majority (V. Lenin n.d). Indeed, In that conference those who were against Lenin's ideas called (MENSHEVIKS) because they were less. Furthermore, by the insistence of Lenin, fight for the dictatorship of “proletariat” was nominated as the main goal of working party. USSR, had a good diplomatic relation with republic of Turkey, and Soviet Union was the first country in the world who officially recognized the Turkey, and Kemal Ataturk had a good relations with Lenin because in the period of revolution in Turkey red army by the command of Lenin helped Turkey with military, economical and geographical sides. Kemal and Lenin had general and same ideas because they wanted to stop and defend their countries from imperialistic countries.

WORLD WAR 2

In 22 of June in 1941 “fashistic” Germany attacked the USSR. The Soviet Government officially announced the war by the radio to the whole population. It was very stressful time because in 1939 fashists had an agreement in Poland, and in that document Germans said that they aren't going to attack the USSR that called (PACT OF RIBBENTROPE). Great Patriotic war continued for 4 years and Soviet Union lost more than 27 millions of people. Before attacking the USSR, fashists occupied the whole Europe to be more military stronger than the USSR. In the period of WW2 Uzbekistan and other republics which were in the part of the Soviet automatically were involved to the war Uzbekistan helped a lot with food and sent many citizens to the war and also accepted more than 1,5 millions of people where 250 thousands were children. The family of SHOMAHMUDOVS is popular because they accepted 14 children. During hard times, USSR was leading by the JOSEPH STALIN, who had knowledge about the war. He deeply studied the military tactics of Suvorov and Napoleon and in that time he made some changes in the economy that more than half of the factories had to manufacture weapons for the war and it was a good decision. Stalin believed to the soldiers that they will win anyway because they had a very patriotic moves and behavior. In the begging of the war USSR were more defensive and then they decided to attack.

Joseph Stalin tried to improve the situation on the war that's why he tried to persuade F.Roosevelt and W.Churchill to attack the western front (FRANCE). But they couldn't reach it for the first time because they thought it is a wrong idea because western side was protected so strongly and too many soldiers would die. In 1945 in the Yalta conference by the idea of

F.Roosevelt 3 major powers came to one place to discuss and find cooperation and F.Roosevelt wanted J.Stalin and W.Churchill be more closer because they didn't like each other.

<https://sovereignty.pl/how-the-yalta-conference-divided-europe-and-pushed-poland-westward>

Explanation:

- 1) W.Churchill (prime minister of UK)
- 2) F.Roosevelt (president of USA)
- 3) J.Stalin (Generalisimus of USSR)

In that conference, Roosevelt recommended to open the organization that will keep the peace in the world. F.Roosevelt, J.Stalin, and W.Churchill were one of the strongest leaders in the history of politics, they were strong and situational leaders because during the WW2 not many countries could save their countries, they promoted stable economy and strong military service so that we can call them as an example for the young generation and many people still try to analyze their leadership style. In 1945, in April soviet union soldiers came to the Berlin. Hitler had no options because western side was destroyed by the USA. In Berlin, so many soldiers died and in every street there was a slaughter. In 3rd of April 1945 soldiers went to the assault and in that day in 22:00 soldiers raised the red flag over Berlin. Hitler killed himself. After that in 8th of May in Berlin, marshal of the Soviet Georgy Zhukov, together with the representatives of American, British and French commands, accepted the surrender of Germany. WW2 ended.

After WW2

Nikita Khrushchev, who came to the authorities after the death of J.Stalin made some reforms. He was an ambitious leader and "patriot". Reforms in his time improved somehow the economy and one of the most popular and significant was constructing the "Khrushchevskys". It means building the apartments in all region they are his symbol because we can still see them in Uzbekistan, Russia, Kazakhstan and so on. But because of problems in an international arena such as: Caribbean crisis and agricultural problems he lost his authority and that's why he had to face collapse.

Leonid Brezhnev, the leader who came after Khrushchev, his ideas were focused on stabilizing the economy improve international authority and also military power. He wanted to reach the socialism and concentrated much on military power. But he also faced troubles: economy developed so slowly, and political parties didn't have connections with the population.

Mikhail Gorbachev, wanted to change the whole system, he wanted to made “perestroika” with the country that would unite and improve the relations with other Soviet republics. But as a result, the Baltic states were the first who officially left the USSR, and then Ukraine, Georgia, Uzbekistan, Azerbaijan, and so on, because the USSR was in a poor economical position and because of wrong policy of Gorbachev.

To Sum up, it was one of the largest countries in the history including 15 republics, and covering Eastern Europe and Northern Asia. The Government controlled most industries, agriculture and system was based on socialism. USSR, was famous for one of the strongest educational system. They left the legacy for each republic and played a huge role in international arena and they even had space achievements sending Yuri Gagarin into space. The USSR was ruled by the Communist party and it dissolved into independent countries in 1991.

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